

Short Communication

Lead accumulation in yard long beans (*vigna unguiculata subsp. sesquipedalis*) and its effect on plant's height

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ABSTRACT

Heavy metal contamination has been a problem for decades because of agricultural and industrial activities. Among heavy metals, lead (Pb) is a potential pollutant that is accumulated in the soil. Many phytoremediation studies have been made to find the most efficient method in the extraction of this metal. For this purpose, this study investigated the accumulation capacity of yard long beans to 3000 ppm lead. After six weeks of germination, the plants were harvested, air-dried, and prepared using the Acid Digestion Method. The samples were tested for lead absorption using the Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) and were statistically analyzed using one-way ANOVA. Results showed that the application of 3000 ppm lead reduces the plants' height by 5.26%. The plant can also accumulate an average of 0.50ppm lead nitrate. In conclusion, the plant's size is not significantly affected by lead concentration. This character inhibited by yard long beans suggested their potential as a phytoremediating agent to lead.

KEYWORDS: *Lead, lead amendments, phytolerant, yard longbeans*

Waste disposal brought about by the agricultural and industrial sector poses a threat to soil fertility by depositing inorganic material and heavy metals. The deposition of heavy metals in the soil increases soil's infertility and the eventual mortality of plants. These heavy metals can be accumulated in plants' roots, taken up into the plant, and enter the food chain, therefore ending human health. These pollutants remain in the soil matrix and become immobile, as in heavy metals (Butterfield, 2009).

Lead is a toxic metal from a number of sources, including the lead in petrol, industrial effluents, and leaching of metal ions from the soil into lakes and rivers by acid rain (Duffus, 2002) as well as extensive use in paints, petrol, explosives, sludge, and industrial wastes (Gupta et al., 2013). Moreover, based on (Shar-

ma and Dubey, 2005), it is a cosmopolitan environment pollutant. According to (Eaton, 1980), significant increases in cultivated soils' lead content have been observed near industrial areas. Further, de (Abreu et al., 1998) said that lead tends to accumulate in the surface ground layer; however, its concentration decreases with soil depth. Based on a study by (David, 2009), lead has the most damaging effects on humans. If humans take up lead-contaminated food or water, lead to lead poisoning occurs when individuals are exposed to Maximum Contaminant Level (MCL). Toxic effects of lead on plants grown on lead-contaminated soils include inhibition of photosynthesis, deficient mineral nutrient uptake, and the problem of water imbalance, which considerably reduce both the vegetative and the reproductive growth of plants (Sharma et al., 2005). It does have not only a significant effect on humans but also plants. Lead treatments caused growth retardation, resulting in reduced leaf area, the major transpiring organ, and reduced transpiration energy, as (Iqbal and Mushtq, 1987) stated. As supported by (Mukhtar, 2010) and (David, 2009), the lead reduced the dry weights of shoot and root, shoot and root length, chlorophyll, and photosynthetic activity.

Researches are conducted to address the problem like contaminated topsoil removal for storage in landfills (Dubey, 2005). However, these processes are very costly (Butterfield, 2009; Kochian, 2000). In like manner, an emerging technology that uses plants to clean up organic or inorganic contaminants in-situ from the soil, surface water, groundwater, and even the atmosphere called phytoremediation had shown to be successful at levels of accumulation thought to be intolerable to plants (Basnet, 2011; Kochian, 2000). Furthermore, this process requires phytotolerant plants that can grow fast, produce high biomass, be harvested easily, and accumulate at a faster rate and higher levels (Basnet, 2009). The plants can be subsequently harvested, processed, and disposed of in an environmentally sound manner.

This study is made to utilize other plants exhibiting *phytotolerance*, which are available in our locality and are related to mung bean (*Vignaradiata*). In

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this study, the accumulation of lead in yard long bean or the local plant “batong” will be tested.

The study's main objective is to determine yard long beans' potential as a phytoremediating agent in the soil. Specifically, this study determines the average level of lead that the plants can accumulate and its effect on the plant's growth rate in terms of height.

This paper used an experimental design using the Acid (Wet) Digestion Method for the preparation and an Atomic Absorption Spectrometry device to determine the average amount of lead concentration and the significant effect of lead on the growth of yard long beans in terms of the height of the two samples. In particular, there were six (6) seeds randomly picked from a single source. These seeds are randomly divided into two groups, and wherein each group comprises three pots with one basis in each pot. These seeds were then placed in a plastic pot. The soil which was used as a controlled sample was also analyzed using flame AAS. There were three controlled samples (not added with lead nitrate $Pb(NO_3)_2$) and three samples added with 3000ppm lead nitrate [$Pb(NO_3)_2$]. The lead (Pb) was obtained from the Chemistry laboratory. Each pot was added continuously with 200 ml distilled water daily and placed under a transparent roof. Growths in height were measured in centimeters weekly for six (6) consecutive weeks. The plants were then harvested, air-dried for one (1) week before cutting into pieces and pounded finely. An amount of 0.6gram, each of the samples was placed in a beaker, added with 10ml concentrated nitric acid (HNO_3), and allowed to stand overnight. It was then heated to a boil until the production of red nitrous ($-NO_2$) fumes has ceased. The samples were cooled and added with 4 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid (HCl), heated again. They were allowed to evaporate to about 10mL and was transferred to a flask and diluted with distilled water. It was then analyzed using Flame-AAS is based on the APHA AWWA-WEF, Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater, 21st Edition (American Public Association, 2005). The data gathered were recorded, tabulated, and imported into the software. It was then treated statistically using the weighted mean- One Factor Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).

As shown in figure 1, the comparison of the means of the plants' height in the control and experimental group showed a slight difference. The control group yields an average growth rate of 14.07 centimeters per week, while the experimental group has 13.33 centimeters per week. A decrease of 5.26% growth rate was observed in the experimental group. In relation to the study of (Mukhtar, 2010) and (David, 2009), the lead reduced the dry weights of shoot and root, shoot and root length, chlorophyll, and photosynthetic activity. Furthermore, (Ahmad, 2008) stressed that lead treatments caused inhibition of the photosynthetic activity and growth

retardation, which results in reduced leaf area, the major transpiring organ. He hence reduced transpiration energy, as stated by (Iqbal and Mushtq, 1987).

Moreover, this inhibitory effect resulted in the slowing down of plant physiological mechanisms, including photosynthesis and chlorophyll content (Ahmad et al., 2008; Mukhtar, 2010), respiration (David, 2009), and translocation. (Mukhtar, 2010) also suggested that the root and shoot growth gradually decreased with increasing metal concentrations. This slight difference was due to the limitation of the main stem of the plants. This insignificance of the two sample groups' height difference implies that the yard long bean was tolerant of leading at 3000 ppm concentration. This was exemplified by (Cunningham and Ow, 1996) that plants had metal-resistant mechanisms through the presence of specific high-affinity ligands, which were reported to make the metal less toxic.

The yard-long beans' absorption level on lead-based on atomic absorption spectroscopy expressed 72.46% absorption of the controlled group due to the initial lead (6.9 ppm) in the soil. In contrast, the experimental group said 1.39% absorption level from the 3006.9 ppm of lead. The increase in lead concentration resulted in a decrease in lead accumulation. These results may be attributed to the inhibitory effect of lead on germination, length of root and shoots, and SDH (Succinate Dehydrogenase) activity (David, 2009) resulting from mustard and mung beans, a relative of yard long beans.

The statistical analysis of the accumulation of lead between the control and the experimental group differed significantly at a 0.5 level of significance, which emphasized a significant difference in the accumulation rate.

This study concludes that yard longbean is a potential phytoremediating agent to lead (Pb), and its height is not significantly affected by the addition of lead in the soil.

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Figure 1. Comparison of the means of the control and the experimental group are presented the same.

Table 1. Analysis of Variance: One Factor ANOVA result of Height

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square Variance	Computed F
Row Factor				
Column Factor	30.450	1	30.450	4.695
Error	32.425		6.485	
Total	62.875			

$F_{(1,4)}$ at $p > 0.05 = 7.71$, $4.695 < 7.71 =$ not significant

Table 2. Atomic Spectrophotometer Readings

Samples	Control Group (0 ppm)				Experimental Group (with 3000 ppm PbNO ₃)			
	c1	c2	c3	Mean	e1	e2	e3	Mean
Lead conc. in ppm	0.09	0.06	0.03	0.06	0.43	0.53	0.53	0.50
Lead concentration in Garden Soil used= 6.9 ppm								

Table 3. Analysis of Variance: One Factor ANOVA result of Lead Absorption

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square Variance	Computed F
Row Factor				
Column Factor	0.2860	1	0.2860	168.2
Error	0.0085		0.0017	
Total	0.2945			

$F_{(1,4)}$ at $P > 0.05 = 7.71$, $168.2 > 7.71 = \text{Significant}$